

Prevalence of Internalized Stigma and Medication Adherence in patients of Obsessive Compulsive Disorder: A Cross Sectional StudyVidisha Singh¹, Siddharth Dixit², Abhinav Kuchhal³¹PG Resident, Department of Psychiatry, Rohilkhand medical college, Bareilly, U.P. India²Professor, Head of Department, Rohilkhand medical college, Bareilly, U.P. India³Associate Professor, Department of Psychiatry, Rohilkhand medical college, Bareilly, U.P. India

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Corresponding Author: Dr. Siddharth Dixit

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Abstract:**Background:** Patients suffering from Obsessive Compulsive Disorder tend to stigmatise themselves which had been linked to poor adherence to treatment.**Aim:** To study internalized stigma and medication adherence in patients of obsessive-compulsive disorder (OCD).**Material and Methods:** A cross-sectional study was conducted on 115 patients diagnosed with OCD at the Department of Psychiatry of Rohilkhand Medical College and hospital, Bareilly, Uttar Pradesh. Samples were collected from patients willing to participate in the study. Patients diagnosed with OCD according to International Classification of Diseases 10th Revision (ICD-10), were included in the study. Upon enrolment, participants provided socio-demographic details after providing written and informed consent. They were then assessed for OCD severity using the Yale-Brown Obsessive Compulsive Scale following this, participants completed the Internalized Stigma of Mental Illness Scale (ISMI) and Medication Adherence Rating Scale (MARS).**Results:** The mean age of the patients were 30+10.38years. Mean duration of illness was found to be 7±3.13 year's. On ISMI scale, the mean score was calculated as 77.84 ± 16.219. The mean Y-BOCS score was determined to be 22.71 ± 5.72. The mean score of medication adherence on MARS scale was 6.01 ± 2.087. There is significant relationship seen between all domains of self-stigma with the severity of OCD psychopathology (p-value<0.001) however, no significant relationship found with severity of OCD with medication adherence. A negative correlation found between all domains of self-stigma with medication adherence.**Conclusion:** Self stigma is found in OCD and can be significant barrier towards road to recovery by affecting medication adherence, more focus should be given on decreasing the internalized stigma and raising the medication compliance through family members, psychoeducation of patients and public.**Keywords:** Obsessive Compulsive Disorder, Internalized Stigma of Mental Illness, Medication Adherence Rating Scale, Yale Brown Obsessive Compulsive Scale.

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Introduction

Stigma derived from Greek word stigmata, which means "a mark of shame or a stain or discredit" and in view of mental illness defined as -multiple dimensions involving feelings, attitudes, and behaviors [1]. Stigma arises from multiple sources, including personal, social, and familial influences, which interact synergistically [2]. These sources of stigma can lead to various complications across different aspects of life. Research indicates that the stigma associated with mental illness often arises due to a lack of understanding or misinformation, as well as the perception of symptoms, such as unusual behavior or agitation, associated with the illness itself [2,3]. Psychiatric cases often suffer from Self stigma. Self-stigma not only lowers their

treatment adherence, self-esteem and self-belief but also contributes to deterioration in the social role obligation and occupational functioning. Individuals with mental illness and other mental health issues face significant stigma, discrimination, marginalization, disadvantage, and vulnerability within our society [1]. The internalized stigma can have profound effects on psychiatric cases, influencing various aspects of the individual's experience and treatment outcomes [4]. Individuals experiencing self-stigma may be hesitant to seek psychiatric help due to fear of judgment, rejection, or discrimination from others. This delay in help-seeking can result in delayed diagnosis, exacerbation of symptoms, and poorer

treatment outcomes [4-6]. Self-stigma negatively impacts medication adherence and treatment engagement. Individuals internalizing negative beliefs about their mental illness may feel unworthy of treatment and doubt medication effectiveness, leading to poor adherence, missed therapy sessions, and increased relapse risk [7]. Individuals with OCD may struggle with medication adherence due to the need for higher doses over longer periods, especially in low- and middle-income countries. Internalized stigma can further hinder drug compliance [8-10]. Self-stigma emerges as a significant obstacle in medication adherence and is associated with increased OCD severity [11]. Other factors, such as symptoms like depression or cognitive impairment, and poor insight into OCD as a disease, may also contribute to treatment non-adherence [12-14] Hence the present study is undertaken to study internalized stigma and medication adherence and to assess the relationship between them in patients with Obsessive compulsive disorder (OCD).

Materials and Methods

A cross-sectional study was conducted from 1 November 2022 to 31 October 2023 at the Department of Psychiatry of Rohilkhand Medical College and hospital, Bareilly, Uttar Pradesh. Samples were collected from Patient swilling to participate in the study. Patients diagnosed with OCD according to International Classification of Diseases 10th Revision (ICD-10), who were on medication for OCD by a qualified psychiatrist during our study period were included in the study. Patients with freshly diagnosed cases of OCD, patients suffering from any other psychiatric comorbidity and patients suffering from any chronic medical illness that may affect the outcome of study were excluded. For patients admitted to the IPD, contact was made within 48 hours of admission, with no subsequent contact. Upon enrolment, participants provided socio-demographic details after providing written and informed consent. They were then assessed for OCD severity using the Yale-Brown Obsessive Compulsive Scale15, which required 10-15 minutes to complete. Following this, participants completed the Internalized Stigma of Mental Illness Scale

(ISMI) [16-17] in approximately 10-15 minutes. Finally, the Medication Adherence Rating Scale (MARS) [18-19] was administered, taking around 5-10 minutes. The total time taken for each participant was approximately 35-40 minutes. The data was coded and entered, it's clearing and compiling was done on a spreadsheet and then it was imported into statistical packaging for social sciences (SPSS) version 23.0 for statistical analysis. Data was analysed by applying frequency, percentage, mean, standard deviation. In our study, statistical correlation was evaluated using spearman correlation coefficient between all three scales (Y-BOCS, ISMI, MARS).

Results

A total of 115 patients of Obsessive- Compulsive Disorder as per ICD-10 criteria were enrolled for study. Table no.1 show the mean age of the patients were 30+10.38years Mean duration of illness was found to be 7±3.13 years and mean age of onset of illness was around 29.38±11.26 years. On Internalized Stigma of Mental Illness Scale (ISMI), the mean score was calculated as 77.84 ± 16.219, 60% of cases had moderate internalized stigma, 29.57% of cases had severe internalized stigma followed by 10.43% of cases had mild internalized stigma with no patients had minimal internalized stigma. OCD severity was assessed using the Yale-Brown Obsessive Compulsive Scale (Y-BOCS). The mean Y-BOCS score was determined to be 22.71 ± 5.72. 13(11.30%) cases were classified as mild, 53(46.09%) as moderate, 45(39.13%) as severe, and 4(3.48%) as extreme. The mean score of medication adherence rating scale (MARS) was 6.01 ± 2.087, 63 patients (54.78%) were adherent and 52 patients(45.22%) were non-adherent. 60.0% study population had internalised stigma falling into moderate category followed by 29.57% in severe category and 10.43% in mild category. A significant relationship was observed between moderate (n=53), severe(n=45) and extreme(n=4) forms of OCD psychopathology on Y-BCOS with self-stigma of all ISMI domains (p-value < 0.05).No significant relationship found with severity of OCD with medication adherence. A negative correlation found between all domains of self-stigma with medication adherence.

Table 1: Socio-Demographic profile of Patients with OCD (N=115)

Socio-Demographic Variables	Number of cases	Percentage %
Age Group (in years)		
12-18 Years	11	9.57
19-30 Years	60	52.17
31-40 Years	27	23.48
41-50 Years	11	9.57
>50 Years	6	5.22
Mean Age30.0 ± 10.38 years		
Gender		
Male	60	52.17

Female	55	47.82
Education		
Illiterate	14	12.17
Primary	18	15.65
Middle School	17	14.78
Secondary	31	26.96
Intermediate	20	17.39
Graduate or above	15	13.04
Marital Status		
Married	70	60.87
Single	45	39.13
Socio-Economic Status		
Upper class	2	1.74
Upper middle	30	26.09
Lower middle	45	39.13
Upper Lower	26	22.61
Lower	12	10.43
Employment Status		
Unemployed	33	28.7
Unskilled Employment	65	56.52
Skilled Employment	17	14.78

Table 2: Severity of Internalised Stigma on ISMI scale (N=115)

ISMI Severity	No. of cases (n)	Frequency (%)
Minimal	0	0
Mild	12	10.43%
Moderate	69	60.0%
Severe	34	29.57%

Table 3: No. of patients adherent on MARS scale (N=115)

Adherence level	No. of cases (n)	Frequency (%)
Adherent (>6)	63	54.78%
Non-adherent (<5)	52	45.22%

Table 4: Score profile of Y-BOCS, ISMI and MARS in patients with OCD (N=115)

	Mean +SD	Score Range
Y-BOCS	22.71+5.72	9-32
ISMI Total	77.84 +16.21	40-117
ISMI Alienation	16.51 +3.86	6-25
ISMI Stereotype Endorsement	17.47+3.86	8-26
ISMI Perceived Discrimination	14.05+2.69	7-21
ISMI Social Withdrawal	15.74+3.50	8-24
ISMI Stigma Resistance	14.05+2.83	7-21
MARS	6.01+2.08	2-9

Table 5: Correlation (Spearman's correlation, r) between severity of OCD (as per Y-BOCS) and domains of Internalized Stigma of Mental Illness Scale (ISMI) in patients with OCD

Y-BOCS (n=115)	(ISMI)						
		Alienation	Stereotype Endorsement	Perceived Discrimination	Social Withdrawal	Stigma Resistance	ISMI total
Mild (n=13)	r-Value	-0.210	-0.099	-0.068	-0.478	-0.072	-0.312
	P-Value	0.490	0.746	0.823	0.098	0.814	-0.299
Moderate (n=53)	r-Value	0.927	0.932	0.841	0.942	0.837	0.866
	P-Value	<0.001*	<0.001*	<0.001*	<0.001*	<0.001*	<0.001*
Severe (n=45)	r-Value	0.463	0.407	0.388	0.438	0.432	0.442
	P-Value	0.001*	0.004*	0.007*	0.002*	0.002*	0.001*
Extreme (n=4)	r-Value	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000

*Statistically significant.

Table 6: Correlation (Spearman's correlation, r) between severity of OCD (as per Y-BOCS) and medication adherence (as per MARS) in patients with OCD (N=115)

Y-BOCS	MARS	
	r-value	p-value
Mild(n=13)	-0.089	0.770
Moderate(n=53)	-0.056	0.692
Severe(n=45)	0.136	0.358
Extreme(n=4)	-0.333	0.666

Table 6 shows no significant relationship observed between different severity levels of OCD psychopathology on Y-BCOS with medication adherence on MARS.

Table 7: Correlation (Spearman's correlation, r) between Internalised stigma and medication adherence.

	Alienation	Stereotype Endorsement	Perceived Discrimination	Social with Drawal	Stigma resistance	ISMI total	P- value
MARS	-0.270	-0.260	-0.310	-0.250	-0.270	-0.270	<0.001

Table 7 shows negative correlation between internalized stigma and medication adherence

Discussion

Obsessive compulsive disorder (OCD) is graded as the fourth most prevalent mental disorder. In Indian population, the rate of prevalence of OCD was found to be 0.6% [20]. In the most populous state of India, Uttar Pradesh, the rate of prevalence of OCD was estimated to be 0.51% [21]. People who suffer from psychiatric illness have issues of both self and social stigma that interferes with the medication adherence and patients suffering from OCD are no exceptions. In presented study total no. of cases enrolled were 115, the majority of cases were in the age group of 19-30 years n=60(52.174%). Similar to our study, Ansari et al. [9] also found the maximum cases in age group of 18 to 30 years n=59(52.67%), suggesting that prevalence in younger adults could be due to the typical age of onset in OCD, which often begins in late adolescence to early adulthood. In current study, we observed majority of cases were males n=60(52.17%), with n=70(60.87%) of cases being married, n=31(30.43%) had completed education up to the secondary school and n=65(56.52%) were engaged in unskilled employment.

Similar trends were noted in the study done by Adewuya AO et al. [14], where a majority of male participants 58.8% were observed, with 43.8% being married and 45.6% having education up to the secondary school level and 60.8% were engaged in semi-skilled occupations. Likewise, Abdisa E. et al. [23] found that more than half 61.7% of the subjects were males, with 34.3% having primary education and 46.7% being jobless. In our study we observed mean ISMI score of 77.84±16.21 falling into moderate category (58-87), this suggests that many patients in our sample

experience self-stigma associated with their condition. Most of the patients in our study fall into moderate category n=69(60%) followed by severe category n=34(29.57%) of internalized stigma indicating substantial self-stigma influenced by societal misconceptions requiring the urgency for targeted interventions to remove stigma and improve patient outcomes. Similar to our study, a study was conducted in Uttar Pradesh population by Ansari E et al. [9] also observed a mean ISMI score of 77.98±10.82. Latalova K et al. [24] also found a mean ISMI score of 69.09±14.47 in patients having OCD. On the other hand in a study by Ociskova M et al. [25] also observed similar findings. This emphasizes the significant impact of self-stigma not only on individuals suffering from OCD but also in individuals coping with severe mental illnesses. In the current study, the maximum mean score was observed in domain of stereotype endorsement (17.47±3.86) (which measures the extent to which respondents agree with common stereotypes associated with mental illness) on ISMI scale.

The elevated Stereotype Endorsement score in our study suggests that individuals with OCD may internalize societal stereotypes about their condition, potentially contributing to feelings of shame and self-stigmatization, however in study done by Ansari E et al. [9] maximum mean score was seen in domain of Alienation (18.71±3.09). Ociskova M et al. [25] also found a comparable score in alienation 15.58±4.33. In our research, the mean Y-BOCS score was 22.71±5.72, indicating the moderate severity of obsessive-compulsive symptoms among patients. Similar to our study, Kaur et al. [26] reported mean Y-BOCS score of 21.39± 3.065 and Ansari E et al. [9] also observed a mean Y-BOCS score of 20.37±8.31, showing a similar range of symptom severity. Our study

observed that with increase in severity of OCD psychopathology, a significant relationship is seen with all domains of internalised stigma (p value < 0.05) suggesting that patients with more severe OCD symptoms are likely to experience higher levels of internalized stigma, affecting different domain such as feelings of alienation, endorsement of stereotypes, perceived discrimination, social withdrawal, and resistance to stigma. Holubova M et al. [15] also reported that severity of disorder is one of the most influencing factors for self-stigma. Within our study the mean MARS score observed was 6.01 ± 2.087 suggests that, on average, patients in our study exhibit a relatively high level of medication adherence indicating that, on average, patients are more likely to adhere to their prescribed medication regimen which can be attributed to the fact that many of patients in our study were educated [13].

Similar to our study, Ansari E et al. [9] also found the high level of medication adherence among their patients with mean MARS score of 6.63 ± 2.360 . In our study no significant relationship found between severity of OCD psychopathology and medication adherence (p -value > 0.05) which might be due to smaller sample size. Contrary to this, Ansari E et al. [9] indicated a negative correlation between the current severity of OCD symptoms and medication adherence, suggesting that medication non-adherence is linked to increased severity of the disorder.

Our study in regards to the relationship between self-stigma and medication adherence noted a negative correlation (p value < 0.001) suggesting that patients with higher levels of internalized stigma demonstrated lower rates of current medication adherence which is also reported in a study done by Ansari E et al. [9], Cinculova et al [27].

Conclusion

Our study outcomes suggest that self-stigma is found in OCD and can be significant barrier towards road to recovery by affecting medication adherence, more focus should be given on decreasing the internalized stigma and raising the medication compliance through family members, psychoeducation of patients and public.

Policymakers should also support the systematic programmes extensively that can curb the issue of stigma in relation to the mental illness in the society thus increasing the social acceptance of patients. These interventions help to decrease the level of self-stigma, thus improving the adherence to treatment and to improve the outcome in our patients.

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